

Assessing methane (CH₄) from Irish agriculture in climate policy 2005–2020 using the GWP₁₀₀ and GWP* greenhouse gas (GHG) metrics

Working Paper summary October 2020

Paul R Price and Barry McMullin, *Dublin City University*

Key Points:

- This analysis compares the use of the GWP₁₀₀ and GWP* GHG metrics in the assessment of Irish agricultural CH₄ emissions. In 2018, 91% of this CH₄ is from cattle (35% from dairy, 56% from beef).
- For the period 2005 (EU ESD base-line year for the national climate target including agriculture) through 2020, the following two scenarios are compared:
 - **ACTUAL:** CH₄ emissions as recorded or projected to 2020 using EPA data.
 - **TARGET:** CH₄ as recorded for 2005–2011 then extrapolated from this period to 2020.
- GWP* emission accounting enables aggregation with other GHGs in all-GHG “CO₂ warming equivalent” (“CO₂-we”) carbon budgets on the basis of *cumulative CO₂-we emissions* from a stated date, allowing for time lag effects.
- However, if this new GWP* GHG metric were to be used in meeting international climate targets then any cumulative basis requires *commonly agreed* conventions for base-year, scenario start and end year, and CH₄ GWP₁₀₀ value.
- *Provided such conventions are made clear* then GWP* **cumulative CO₂-we** can more accurately reflect CH₄ warming or warming reduction outcomes than GWP₁₀₀.
- Use of GWP₁₀₀ and GWP* *both* clearly show a reduction in Irish agricultural CH₄ emissions up to 2011 and then a sharp reversal to rapidly increasing CH₄, resulting from government policy endorsement of sectoral agricultural strategy. Emissions are projected to rise further from 2020 due to further dairy expansion.
- Use of GWP* shows the extent of this national climate policy failure since 2010 more starkly than GWP₁₀₀. In effect the policy change has undone 20 years of mitigation effort, delaying agricultural transition.
- **The current flow of Irish agricultural methane is responsible for an ongoing contribution to global warming that has the equivalent warming to over 1,300 MtCO₂, a level equivalent to 30 years of Ireland's current energy CO₂ emissions.**
- Achieving substantial and sustained reductions in aggregate ruminant CH₄ emissions and fugitive manure and biomethane anaerobic digestion is therefore a very important mitigation lever that Ireland can utilise in climate action policy to constrain emissions.
- Policy to ensure substantial reductions in total reactive nitrogen inputs can drive CH₄ (and N₂O) reduction.
- **This analysis confirms the crucial role of sustained agricultural CH₄ mitigation as an essential policy lever in effective societal climate action for Ireland aligned with the Paris Agreement and the SDGs.**

Context:

Irish agricultural CH₄ resulted in emissions of 519 ktCH₄ in 2018 (462 ktCH₄ from enteric fermentation and 57 ktCH₄ from manure management) – almost entirely from 1.5 million dairy cows, 5.8 million beef cattle, and 5.1 million sheep. Multiplied by a GWP₁₀₀ value of 25 (as currently used in UNFCCC reporting) this equates to 13 MtCO₂eq in reported EPA inventory of GWP₁₀₀ emissions [5].

GWP₁₀₀ metric values are directly related to the annual quantity of CH₄ released, so they usefully show the annual emissions to be reduced through policy and measures. However, GWP₁₀₀ incorrectly suggests CO₂-like warming behaviour for CH₄, so it does not accurately show the rapid near-term global warming response resulting from changes in CH₄ emissions, nor does it show the large warming reduction potential that can be enabled by sustained CH₄ emission reductions over time. Sustained CH₄ mitigation at a faster reduction rate than about -0.3%/yr results in warming reduction equating to CO₂ removals. It is incorrect to refer to such a reduction in CH₄ warming as “cooling”.

Due to these deficiencies in using GWP₁₀₀ for CH₄ and other short-lived climate pollutants, a GHG metric called GWP* has been developed by an Oxford University group [1]. GWP* does not provide any new climate science understanding of CH₄'s climate behaviour, rather it provides a new formula that enables the resultant warming or warming reduction impact of CH₄ to be estimated directly from the existing national GWP₁₀₀ CO₂-eq time series data in a way that approximates the climate system response, *on the basis of cumulative CO₂ warming equivalent emissions* [1]. A change to use of the GWP* metric rather than GWP₁₀₀ to report CH₄ emissions has been advocated by Oxford scientists [2]. However, recent work at Dublin City University [3] does not support this view for international GHG accounting at this time, though the DCU work does support the use of GWP* for national or sectoral policy comparison of scenarios including CH₄. Others have also suggested the naïve use of the GWP* metric in international emissions accounting could result in unintentional unfairness [4].

Using the GWP* metric it is trivial to show that the ongoing global warming contribution from methane in CO₂ warming equivalent terms is approximately 80 times its current year's GWP₁₀₀ value. This gives an approximate estimate of the maximum potential mitigation available from a permanent cut in this flow. Based on the GHG₁₀₀ value of 32 used by Lynch et al. (2020) and the 2018 EPA-reported GWP₁₀₀ value, the current flow of Irish agricultural methane is responsible for an ongoing contribution to global warming that has the equivalent warming of over 1,300 MtCO₂. This warming level is equivalent to over 30 years of Ireland's current energy CO₂ emissions, indicating that achieving near-term substantial and sustained reductions in agricultural CH₄ emissions is a very important potential mitigation lever that Ireland can utilise in climate action to limit imminent overshoot of Ireland's Paris-aligned, all-GHG national carbon quota [3].

Analysis of Irish agricultural CH₄ scenarios, 2005–2020, using GWP₁₀₀ and GWP*:

Based on EPA inventory and projections of agricultural CH₄ data (5), two scenarios are compared: an ACTUAL scenario for the actual pathway of agricultural CH₄ emissions from 2005 to 2020; and, a comparison, counterfactual TARGET scenario assuming

that the actual straight line annual CH₄ emission reduction as achieved from 2005 to 2011 continued by extrapolation through to 2020. This target scenario would result in an emission reduction slightly greater than the 20% *pro rata* reduction for 2020 relative to 2005 under the national EU climate target. As in Ref [1] a GWP₁₀₀ of 32 is used.

Figure 1: Scenarios by annual CH₄ using GWP100

In Figure 1, from 2005 to 2011 the ACTUAL CH₄ emissions and TARGET pathway are the same but they diverge sharply from 2011 onward. For this scenario, comparison emissions are assumed to level out at the level reached in 2020, the scenarios' end-year.

Figure 2: Scenarios by annual CH₄ using GWP*

Figure 2 shows the same scenario emissions pathways as in Figure 1, but here using the GWP* formula whereby CO₂-we values are calculated from GWP₁₀₀ CO₂-eq time series of annual emission values. GWP* annual values are affected by the GWP₁₀₀ value 20 years previously. To prevent this 20-year lag effect due to prior years from influencing the analysis, all 20 years prior to 2005 are assumed to have the same annual CH₄ emissions as 2005, thereby setting the change in CH₄ flow prior to 2005 to zero for the compared scenarios.

Figure 3: Scenarios by cumulative CO₂-eq and CO₂-we

Figure 3, above, shows cumulative emissions from 2005 using GWP₁₀₀ and GWP* for both scenarios for the period 2005 to 2020. Note, the 2005 start value is set to zero but the GWP* 2005 global warming contribution of Irish agriculture CH₄ is ~1500 MtCO₂-we. Emissions are run to 2040 to show the full 20-

year lag effect on resultant warming due to the comparison period emissions. Even though the **TARGET** scenario's annual CH₄ emissions decrease over time, the cumulative GWP₁₀₀ pathway incorrectly shows increased resultant warming, whereas GWP* correctly shows reduced warming for this scenario. The GWP* metric reveals an even larger degree of divergence between the target (mitigation) and actual (emissions increase) pathways than through use of GWP₁₀₀. Following the **TARGET** scenario to 2020 would have resulted in a *warming reduction* equivalent to a one-off removal of 115 MtCO₂ by 2040, whereas **ACTUAL** CH₄ emissions resulted in a warming increase equivalent to one-off emissions of 265 MtCO₂ by 2040: a total GWP* scenario difference by 2040 equating to one-off emission of 380 MtCO₂ (~10 years of Ireland's fossil carbon emissions, three times larger than the 120 MtCO₂-eq scenario difference indicated by the GWP₁₀₀ metric.

Discussion:

This analysis of CH₄ emissions shows that Irish Government policy endorsement of agri-food industry-led agri-strategy since 2010 has resulted in increasing agricultural CH₄ emissions, contrary to national climate objectives. Ireland's agricultural sector *had* been aligned with meeting a *pro rata* EU national mitigation target pathway from 2005 to 2011, but this was reversed thereafter by policy. **Both GWP₁₀₀ and GWP* show that the 13 years of mitigation over 1997–2011 has been more than completely cancelled out due to dairy expansion and agricultural intensification since 2010.** Greater use of nitrogen fertiliser, enabling more grass feedstock growth, has resulted in increased cattle CH₄ emissions. Use of either GHG metric shows how agricultural strategy in Ireland since 2010 has resulted in an ill-advised reversal in climate action policy in Ireland, completely undoing prior mitigation achieved in agriculture. As shown here, a GWP* warming equivalent analysis simply shows this reversal even more starkly.

As yet, the use of GWP* is insufficiently developed to be applied to international accounting. Single year or short-run annual CO₂-we values are not meaningful in policy analysis. Nonetheless, GWP* is useful for comparison of alternative climate mitigation plans *from a given base year* as it enables inclusion of the **cumulative CO₂-we** warming or warming reduction impact of CH₄ into policy carbon budgets and national quota fair shares related to the Paris temperature targets [3]. **Therefore, when GWP* is used, it is particularly important to focus on the policy outcome based on cumulative CO₂-we emissions. As is evident from use of GWP* in this analysis, this requires a common base reference year, such as the EU target's reference to 2005 as used in this briefing, including the full 20-year lagged effect of CH₄ forcing.**

References:

1. [Lynch J et al. \(2020\) Demonstrating GWP*. Env Res Lett](#)
2. [Oxford Martin School \(2020\) Get the maths right on emissions or risk missing temperature target.](#)
3. [McMullin B, Price P \(2020\) Assessing society-wide national climate change mitigation scenarios including methane](#)
4. [Rogelj J, Schleussner C-F. \(2019\) Unintentional unfairness when applying new GHG metrics at country level. Environ Res Lett](#)
5. [Duffy P, et al. \(2020\) IRELAND NATIONAL INVENTORY REPORT 2020.](#)